

THE INFLUENCE OF VIRTUAL GAMES ON THE MINDS OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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Abstract: In this article, it has come into our lives and our society virtualization is widespread among all layers of our living and it talks about its impact on our way of life and its negative aspects, and about the evils caused by virtual games, which lead to destruction and kill young people.

Key words: internet, electronic games, social networks, popular culture, addiction, computer technology,

In the 21st century, the ideological landscape of the world has changed radically, and the acceleration of global integration processes requires a new way of thinking. To form feelings of love for the Motherland in the minds of young people and teenagers, to explain that independence is a great blessing, to be able to make sacrifices for the benefit of the nation and people, to understand the essence and value of our independence, to protect it from any danger. Education of an independent, free-thinking, spiritually and physically healthy person who considers preservation as his sacred duty, has a deep knowledge of a specific specialty, profession, is becoming one of the urgent tasks. This requires forming the skills of objective assessment of historical reality and drawing correct conclusions in young people.

At the same time, the penetration of various destructive ideas aimed at capturing the hearts and minds of young people is becoming more visible, especially through the Internet. This process is also related to the increasing interest of our children in computer technologies and various computer games. Propagators of destructive ideas are trying to use these interests effectively for their goals. In other words, the extremists, who are well aware that "gaming" is a threat to a certain part of society, are trying to occupy the minds of teenagers and young people in this way.

"Scientists I. P. Korolenko and T. A. Donskikh classified the signs of playfulness as follows:

1. An increase in the amount of time a teenager spends in the game
2. The previous habits and interests are narrowed and he thinks more about the game;
3. Not being able to leave the game even if he wins or loses;
4. Looking forward to the start of the game, getting restless and nervous when there is no game;

5. The desire to play more and more, to go to the game more and more
6. Being unable to stop playing. "It's enough, I quit the game," he says, but when he sees his partners who played together before, when the game is discussed, he quickly changes his mind while passing by the playground;
7. Lying and stealing from parents to get money for gambling;
8. Lying and hiding his excessive playfulness from family members, doctors, and others is a sign of a teenager's playfulness."

It can be seen that in most cases, a child can be lost as a result of not taking a serious approach to education during adolescence, and indifference to the child's behavior. After all, not only bigotry, but also the origin of various diseases are observed as a result of "playfulness" or indulgence in various informational games. In other words, as a result of the passion for internet games, negative consequences such as stroke, ludomania, mental illnesses, and in most cases death due to a ruptured heart are visible. This is one of the biggest threats to our developing country.

Therefore, it is very important to properly organize the education process, to constantly monitor the child's upbringing. It is impossible to completely restrict the Internet to a child.

Internet is the demand of the times. Nowadays, the Internet has become a part of our life. The Internet has many eases and conveniences for us. It makes our distance close to us and we are looking for all the information we need on the Internet. How we use the Internet is up to us. Just as everything has its benefits, it also has its disadvantages. Not everyone is using the internet for good these days. Effects of virtual video games on the Internet on youth. It brings a future to their spiritual mind and spirit. The American Medical Association intends to officially list addiction to video games as a mental retardation. According to doctors, this disease threatens the health of anyone who plays games for more than two hours a day. This also applies to those who seek entertainment on the Internet. The fact that computer games are more popular than ever and their negative impact on young people is one of the problems that have been worrying medical professionals for a long time.

For a person who spends hours and days sitting at the computer and "wins" various virtual prizes and achievements, they begin to acquire a truly valuable meaning. Such points and achievements are sold and bought among "loyal" players. A lot of money is spent on such work. For example, an Australian student named David Storr bought a virtual island for 35,000 US dollars. This island has an old castle, several bathing spots and special places to hunt various creatures. But these places are only in the imagination, only on the computer screen.

Many games are built on the basis of scenes of brutal killing of people and animals and bloodshed. Such sad pictures have a strong negative impact not only on the minds of young people, but also on the minds of the elderly. The fact that some of those who played games like "GTA", "Sniper", "Killer" and others later became real killers is a clear proof of our opinion.

In addition, we often hear through the mass media: schoolchildren and teenagers in Western countries are causing the death of their parents, teachers, and peers. It is a bitter truth that such terrible events are the poisonous fruit of the "education" that Western children are given in the virtual world.

Immersion in futile and harmful activities such as computer games is condemned by Islam. Because as a result, the child's faith weakens, he becomes a slave of the devil and works according to his tricks. As a result, he himself will die. Therefore, we should think about it and think about it.

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